

ON DYNAMICS OF A CUBIC STOCHASTIC OPERATORS IN S^2

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu ishda biz ikki o'lchamli simpleksda aniqlangan volterra kubik stoxastik operatorni o'rganamiz. Ya'ni, simpleksda aniqlangan kubik stoxastik operatorini ko'rib chiqamiz. Ikki o'lchamli simpleksda aniqlangan volterra kubik stoxastik operator uchun simpleksning uchlari qo'zg'almas nuqtalar ekanligi ko'rsatilgan.

Abstract: In this article, we study the Volterra cubic stochastic operator defined on a two-dimensional simplex. That is, we consider the cubic stochastic operator defined on a simplex. It is shown that for the Volterra cubic stochastic operator defined on a two-dimensional simplex, the vertices of the simplex are fixed points.

There are many systems which are described by nonlinear operators. A quadratic stochastic operator (QSO) is one of the simplest nonlinear cases.

Let $E = \{1, 2, \dots, m\}$ be a finite set and the set of all probability distribution on E

$$S^{m-1} = \left\{ x = (x_1, \dots, x_m) \in \mathbb{R}^m : x_i \geq 0, \sum_{i=1}^m x_i = 1 \right\} \quad (1)$$

be the $(m-1)$ -dimensional simplex. *Cubic stochastic operator.* The CSO is a mapping $W : S^{m-1} \rightarrow S^{m-1}$ of the form

$$x'_l = \sum_{i,j,k=1}^m P_{ijk,l} x_i x_j x_k, \quad l \in E, \quad (2)$$

where $P_{ijk,l}$ are coefficients of heredity such that

$$P_{ijk,l} \geq 0, \quad \sum_{l=1}^m P_{ijk,l} = 1, \quad \forall i, j, k \in E. \quad (3)$$

and we suppose that the coefficients $P_{ijk,l}$ do not change for any permutation of i, j, k .

The Volterra CSO $W : S^2 \rightarrow S^2$ is:

$$W : \begin{cases} x'_1 = x_1(1+x_2)(1+x_3), \\ x'_2 = x_2(1-x_3)\left(1+\frac{1}{2}x_1\right), \\ x'_3 = x_3(1-x_1)\left(1-\frac{1}{2}x_2\right). \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

Let a face of the simplex S^2 be the set $\Gamma_\alpha = \{\mathbf{x} \in S^2 : x_i = 0, i \notin \alpha \subset \{1,2,3\}\}$.

Let the set $\text{int } S^2 = \{\mathbf{x} \in S^2 : x_1x_2x_3 > 0\}$ and let the set $\partial S^2 = S^2 \setminus \text{int } S^2$ be the interior and the boundary of the simplex S^2 , respectively. Let $\mathbf{e}_1 = (1,0,0)$, $\mathbf{e}_2 = (0,1,0)$, $\mathbf{e}_3 = (0,0,1)$ be the vertexes of the two-dimensional simplex.

Lemma. *For the SCSO W (4), the following assertions true:*

- (i) *The face $\Gamma_{\{1,2\}}$, $\Gamma_{\{1,3\}}$, $\Gamma_{\{2,3\}}$ of the simplex S^2 are invariant sets;*
- (ii) $\text{Fix}(W) = \{\mathbf{e}_1, \mathbf{e}_2, \mathbf{e}_3\}$;

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